

Lost in space but not in data: Tracking Technology Trends in the Space Field

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Monitoring technology trends is essential for the European Space Agency (ESA) to fulfill its mission of advancing Europe's space capabilities. Yet, in a rapidly evolving ecosystem where information is scattered across various databases and formats this is no easy task. In this study we present a novel approach to predict and track the technologies related to ESA R&D studies, based on the ESA Technology Tree. Leveraging pre-trained Large Language Models (LLMs) from OpenAI and Mistral AI, we demonstrate how to enrich a database with technology-related information, providing fresh insight into technology trends.

1 Introduction

The European space sector is a highly complex and quickly developing ecosystem involving a variety of stakeholders (e.g., agencies, companies, and universities). Being able to navigate and comprehend this ecosystem is essential for the development of Europe's space capabilities, e.g., by identifying technology gaps ("what are we missing?") or our heritage ("what has already been done?").

A major source of information assisting decision makers in navigating this landscape are curated databases providing insights into the design of past and on-going space missions, stakeholders and their products, as well as research activities. Many such databases exist, usually focusing on a specific sub-domain, e.g., the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) database [1], the Nebula library [2] tracking the European Space Agency's (ESA) R&D activities with industrial and academic partners, and the esa-match [3] platform with information on entities doing business with ESA.

In practice, there are still many challenges regarding the interoperability of such databases: entries are often incomplete and prone to incorrect information –

a side effect of the non-trivial assembly process which includes manual editing (by various people) as well as data integration from sources of differing quality, content, and completeness.

To better classify and cross-reference different technologies, ESA uses a controlled vocabulary taxonomy, the Technology Tree [4], which is applied over several ESA platforms for several purposes: tagging R&D activities, listing suppliers and internal expertise, or harmonizing technology roadmaps. However, a large fraction of entries in the platforms have trivial labels (like "Other") or are not labelled at all (incomplete entries), making it hard to cross-reference activities using these categories [5]. Similarly, when merging different databases, their attributes rarely overlap perfectly – meaning that specific information available in one database might be completely missing in another one. Specifically in our use-case, non-ESA databases containing information about R&D projects and space technologies do not provide the labels from the ESA Technology Tree. This prevents a syntactically meaningful integration of databases, where users, reasoning engines, and inference tools could harness the integrated information to provide a more holistic view of the space ecosystem.

In this work, we propose the use of pre-trained Large Language Models (LLMs) [6, 7] to predict such missing information in databases not only for clean-up, but to increase the compatibility of different data sources and facilitate their integration. More specifically, we phrase this challenge as a text completion problem. If a certain attribute (like "Technology Domain") is missing, we let the LLM predict this attribute providing additional information on its related attributes (e.g., an activity description) and using the ESA Technology Tree. In this work, we limit our study to the Nebula library, but the presented approach translates immediately to other types of databases.

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Family	Model	Parameters	Context (Tokens)	Release Date	Access	Input/Output Cost (Per 1M tokens)
GPT	GPT-3.5 Turbo	n/a	16k	06.23	API	\$0.5/\$1.5
	GPT-4 Turbo	n/a	128k	11.23	API	\$10/\$30
	GPT-4o	n/a	128k	05.24	API	\$5/\$15
Mistral	Mistral 7b	7B	32k	09.23	Open/API	\$0.25/\$0.25
	Mixtral 8x22B	39B	64k	04.24	Open/API	\$2/\$6
	Mistral Large	n/a	32k	02.24	API	\$4/\$12

Table 1: Comparison of the LLMs prompted in this study (*Indicated costs valid on the 23rd of May 2024).

2 Method

2.1 Data

The *Nebula Public* library contains information about over 1,200 R&D activities funded by ESA. Each entry contains a description of the study and can be classified using the technology domain (TD) labels. Not all activities are classified, and only the 276 activities that list at least one technology domain are considered for this study. The Technology Tree [4] is a taxonomy maintained by the ESA Technology Coordination and Planning Office. It defines a technology as "the technical know-how that is required for the design, manufacture and test of a space product, including all related processes". It has 3 levels of classification, but for the purpose of this experiment only the 26 top level TDs were considered.

2.2 Approach

A pre-trained LLM is provided with the description of a Nebula activity and a list of categories corresponding to the 26 top level TDs of the ESA technology tree. The model is requested to predict which category (or categories) the text belongs to, with no specific order of relevance since the TDs are not ranked in the original dataset. The descriptions only consists of text, therefore there is no multi-modal dimension here.

2.3 LLM Selection

We evaluate six models from OpenAI [8] and Mistral AI [9]. The parameters of the selected LLMs are detailed in Table 1. These models were chosen as their performances are well recognised in the community. As of the 25th of May 2024, the GPT-4o and GPT-4 Turbo models were respectively first and second on the LMSYS Chatbot Arena Leaderboard [10] while Mixtral-8-22B was second on the HuggingFace's Open LLM Leaderboard[11].

2.4 Prompting Strategy

Two versions of the same basic prompt were used. Version 1 only provided the technology domain class names to the model, while version 2 provided the class names and a short description of each class.

You are a space systems engineer trying to identify the key technologies mentioned in a text based on an existing classification system. Given the list of technology classes, propose a class for the piece of text. If you think none of the categories are applicable, do not propose any classes. You can propose more than one class if you think a text matches two classes well. Do not provide an explanation or reasoning for the results. Return the result as a list with the following syntax: [class1, class2, ...]

Extra instructions are provided in the prompt to adjust the format of the response provided and ensure that the model does not add explanations, or come up with its own categories.

2.5 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of the different LLMs and prompting strategies, we use the F1 score for top 3 predictions. Thus, given a list of technology domains predicted by a LLM for a single activity, we check whether the ground truth is part of the (up to) first 3 predicted elements. If true, the LLM succeeded in predicting the technology domain of this activity; otherwise it failed and the first element of the list is used as its predicted technology domain.

The F1-score is given by the harmonic mean of the recall and precision, ranging from 0 to 1 – with 0 being the worst and 1 being the best score. In our case, recall reflects how often on average the correct TD is part of the top 3 predictions of the LLM. Precision captures the tendency of the model to retrieve the relevant TDs over all retrieved TDs, i.e., number of true positives over the number of true positives and false positives.

2.6 Software

This work is based on a migration of the Nebula library to a Neo4j Knowledge Graph (KG) [12]. As this is a research project we used the Neo4j community edition. Our KG also contains data from other sources (e.g., esa-match [3], CEOS [1]), but those were outside the scope of this analysis and are therefore left aside.

We utilised some functions from the Neo4j NaLLM library [13] to refine part of the LLM API calls. We relied on the OpenAI and Mistral AI Python APIs to prompt the models [6, 7]. Finally, to compute the evaluation metrics, we used the scikit-Learn Python library [14].

3 Results

For validation, the predictions are run 3 times for each model and each prompting strategy. The average F1-score and standard deviation are reported in Figure 1 for the GPT and Mistral models. Only the results for the most salient labels in the dataset (above 5 % representation in labels) are reported in this paper. As a baseline, we used uniform sampling over 100 runs, achieving F1-scores ranging between 0.11 and 0.16 for the most salient TDs.

We also compare our approach to a sentence embedding strategy based on the *paraphrase-MiniLM-L6-v2* model from the Sentence Transformers Python library [15]. Using this model we embed each activity's description, and compare it with the embeddings of the TD definition through a cosine similarity measure.

No model was a clear out-performer, instead they seem to have different performances on different classes, with performance averaging out between 0.5 and 0.6 for all the models. Overall, performance drops with Prompt 2, where the class descriptions are provided. Although our sample size is low, the models seem to give consistent answers, with little variation between subsequent model runs.

All models outperform the baseline uniform sampling strategy. Overall, the LLMs prompting achieved higher performances than the sentence embedding approach, except for certain categories where smaller LLMs were outperformed (e.g., with Mistral 7B for the *System Design and Verification* label, considering both prompting strategies).

The authors spent approximately €130 in different API credits for all stages of this work

4 Discussion

Varying results were obtained for each label and model, although the F1-scores of all LLMs signifi-

cantly outperform our naive baseline strategy (randomly guessing) – indicating that already the smaller (and hence cheaper) models perform sufficiently for this task. The models fell short for the technologies whose categorisations are highly dependent on the space context (e.g., ‘Automation, Telepresence & Robotics’ or ‘Mission Operation & Ground Data Systems’), although it is to be noted that all used technology descriptions are highly specialised to the space field. The GPT and Mistral models displayed pre-existing knowledge of the context and goals of both the Nebula library and the ESA Technology Tree. This might explain the minimal (to none or negative) impact on performances when we used the 2nd prompt type. In addition, the second prompt increased the cost of the predictions, having more input tokens. We also noticed that the GPT-4o, GPT-4 Turbo and Mistral Large models had a higher tendency to deviate from the required output format and were attempting to justify their reasoning. We solved this problem by adding the sentence ‘Do not provide an explanation or reasoning for the results.’.

Overall, the models showed robust and reliable performance on the studied task. Unfortunately, the content of the pre-training corpora for both GPT and Mistral families of models are not disclosed. We expect – or rather rely on the fact – that knowledge about the space industry and space missions is contained within this corpus. However, we cannot fully rule out that parts of the Nebula library and ESA's Technology Tree were part of this corpus. Still, we are confident that the LLMs did not have full knowledge of this data. For instance, they were not able to list the ESA Technology Tree or individual Nebula database entries. To reduce the risk of cross-contamination between the employed testing data and the LLM's pre-training corpus, we will apply our approach to non-public data in future studies.

In future work, we are interested in exploring chain of thought prompting to improve model performance, and to better understand the categorisation mechanisms. Moreover, we wish to investigate additional prompting strategies, notably a few-shot approach: providing examples of Nebula activities and their assigned technology domains in addition to the basic prompt. Finally, we aim to explore the performances of additional families of models, in particular the LLaMA [16] and PaLM [17] models.

5 Conclusion

LLMs, and foundation models in general, are currently taking the spotlight in the AI field. Their capabilities to interpolate well across text generation

Figure 1: F1 scores averaged over 3 runs per most salient TDs (standard deviation as error bar).

tasks makes them intriguing candidates for solving challenges such as those discussed in this paper – potentially allowing us to autonomously clean and integrate vast amount of information sources.

Although using LLMs as 0-shot classifiers might introduce errors in records, they could be integrated as an improvement to User Experience (UX) to help human documentalists in proposing tags and classes for entries in databases, as well as collecting feedback to improve future classifications. The flexibility of the approach means that new controlled vocabularies and classification schemes could be easily integrated in the databases by changing how the LLMs are prompted and which information it is instructed to look for.

Further studies still have to be performed to validate and solidify the generalisation capabilities of LLMs, mostly because the used training data is not publicly available. Nevertheless, the presented results indicate that LLMs are a crucial puzzle piece for assembling a holistic and reliable model of the space ecosystem that helps decision makers and engineers successfully shape the future of Europe in space.

Contributions

All authors were involved in designing the study and writing the paper. AB wrote the Python script of the experiment pipeline and designed the prompt strategies. AB and AVL wrote the code for parsing and processing the database. AB performed experiments with GPT 3.5 Turbo and GPT 4-o, AVL with GPT 4 Turbo, and DD with the Mistral models.

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